

Co-Creation Toolkit for Environmental Services

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Link to toolkit:

<https://nerc-eds.github.io/co-creation-toolkit/>

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About this work

The BOOST EDS project, [funded by UKRI and supported by DSIT](#), aimed to pilot a range of measures to address issues of data findability, traceability, accessibility and interoperability, to improve data sharing and access across disciplines. Conducted from late 2023 to March 2025, the project consisted of five work packages, with one work package dedicated to user centred approaches in the context of environmental data services. The work was undertaken by members of the NERC Environmental Data Service (EDS).

This is a summary report to provide supporting information to the overarching report - User centred approaches for environmental data services: embedding co-creation and collaboration (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15115280>)

Summary

We have created a ‘user-centred design toolkit for environmental services’ with the aim of supporting data, software and design experts to create user-friendly and effective environmental data services. This toolkit provides a range of resources, case studies and guidance needed to collaborate with users, gather insights, and co-design solutions that work. The toolkit has been shaped by collaborations across all environmental science domains, with a range of experts in user design, data management, communications and engagement, and software engineering.

The toolkit is still in early development. We are looking to share our progress so far and understand if this is something the wider community would like to contribute to or partake in, as a community of practice.

Rationale for the work

To address the unique UX challenges of environmental data projects and empower user-centric design of effective environmental data products and services, bridging the gap where existing resources fall short.

Homepage of the Co-Creation Toolkit

The main page of the toolkit allowing users to choose topics and then relevant articles

Methodology

The toolkit's creation was a collaborative effort, born from shared experiences and a commitment to co-creation. It began with internal knowledge sharing, where lessons learned across various data centres were discussed and common environmental data challenges identified. Relevant topics for the toolkit were then prioritised. A key step involved presenting the toolkit in a workshop setting to gather feedback from potential users. This iterative process of development, feedback, and refinement continues. The toolkit is continually developed based on user feedback and needs, reflecting the co-creation principles it promotes.

A part of the Creating User Stories toolkit explaining how the article is laid out

Overview

User stories are a powerful tool for building digital products that meet the needs of your users. This post will guide you through the **key steps in creating user stories**, from understanding their structure to prioritising and testing them.

Outline:

- [When to use user stories?](#)
- [When NOT to use user stories?](#)
- [Why User Stories Are Effective](#)
- [Components of a User Story](#)
- [Steps for Creating User Stories](#)
- [User Story Checklist](#)
- [Tips for Effective User Stories](#)

Why User Stories?

Environmental data often involves complex scientific concepts and diverse stakeholders. User stories facilitate collaboration between scientists, product owners, developers, and users to ensure the data product or service meets real-world needs.

Review from the perspective of non-UX researcher/designer

The intended audience of the toolkit is people working with or supporting environmental data, so that they can improve the UX and design of environmental data services. However, the toolkit and its case studies have been written by UX researchers and designers. Therefore, in order to improve the readability of the toolkit, the case studies were reviewed by a non-UX researcher or designer. This was done over the course of a couple of months towards the end of the project.

Lessons learnt

In the review, the case studies were found to be a useful set of examples of performing UX research with methods, resources, and results clearly laid out with consistent sections for each case study. The case studies often include a link to an interactive prototype which was found to be really valuable for getting to try out the results of a sprint or project. Each case study is labelled with the organisation in which it was produced, although there are no individual authors visible.

The main issue that was found across the case studies was the assumptions made by the authors about the audience. Organisation-specific teams are named but not explained who they consist of and acronyms are used without explaining their full names. For example, in the “Devon Design Sprint” case study, the author never explains what “Devon” refers to and in the “Multi-Organisation Content Management System for Hazard Data” case study, the author uses “INHFL” and “DST” without defining them. This means that the context for some of the case studies is confusing for people reading from outside the relevant organisation.

Activities

We set out to investigate how data and digital tools can help consider and understand the effects that land use decisions have on carbon sequestration and storage in the context of soil, woodland/ forestry and peatlands.

The user journey for two key user groups – Land Managers and Land User Influencers

We ran the design sprint for a full five days. This was necessary due to the complex nature of the challenge being solved. For less demanding challenges and stakeholders with prior design sprint experience, a shorter sprint of 2 or 3 days is also viable.

The goal of the first day was to encourage everyone to share what they already know and develop a common understanding with the rest of the group. By starting at the beginning (even if some people are already familiar with the problem), it nudges the group into a beginner’s mindset and leads to fresh solutions.

A part of the Devon Design Sprint case study explaining how they ran the sprint

One accessibility issue found across the toolkit was a lack of alt-text in diagrams and article cover images. Alt-text would be useful as a lot of the diagrams are important for understanding the points made in the case studies and aren’t accessible at present. For example, in the “Personas - Land InSight” case study, the personas themselves are presented as images, while the text around them just provides an overview. The same point stands for the article cover images, although some of these are purely decorative. There is one video included in the “Designing Geospatial Data Portals”

case study which could be improved by including a transcript. Opportunities and future recommendations

The toolkit provides a foundation for improving environmental data products. Future recommendations could include expanding the toolkit with more specific examples, case studies, and resources tailored to different environmental domains, as well as developing training programmes on how to effectively use the toolkit's resources. At the moment, the case studies all come from teams in BGS, but it could expand to projects from other NERC centres. Promoting the toolkit and encouraging contributions from the community would also be useful.

Supporting materials

Co-Creation Toolkit Website: <https://nerc-eds.github.io/co-creation-toolkit/>

Source code for Co-Creation Toolkit: <https://github.com/NERC-EDS/co-creation-toolkit>